

Large Language Models for Intelligent RDF Knowledge Graph Construction: Results from Medical Ontology Mapping

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2 ABSTRACT

3 The exponential growth of digital data, particularly in specialized domains like healthcare,
4 necessitates advanced knowledge representation and integration techniques. RDF knowledge
5 graphs offer a powerful solution, yet their creation and maintenance, especially for complex
6 medical ontologies like SNOMED CT, remain challenging. Traditional methods often struggle
7 with the scale, heterogeneity, and semantic complexity of medical data. This paper introduces
8 a methodology leveraging the contextual understanding and reasoning capabilities of LLMs to
9 automate and enhance medical ontology mapping for RDF knowledge graph construction. We
10 conduct a comprehensive comparative analysis of six systems—GPT-4o, Claude 3.5 Sonnet
11 v2, Gemini 1.5 Pro, Llama 3.3 70B, DeepSeek R1 and BERTMap—using a novel evaluation
12 framework that combines quantitative metrics (precision, recall, F1-score) with qualitative
13 assessments of semantic accuracy. Our approach integrates a data preprocessing pipeline
14 with an LLM-powered semantic mapping engine, utilizing BioBERT embeddings and ChromaDB
15 vector database for efficient concept retrieval. Experimental results on a dataset of 108 medical
16 terms demonstrate the superior performance of modern LLMs, particularly GPT-4o, achieving a
17 precision of 93.75% and an F1-score of 96.26%. These findings highlight the potential of LLMs
18 in bridging the gap between structured medical data and semantic knowledge representation,
19 towards more accurate and interoperable medical knowledge graphs.

20 **Keywords:** LLM, ontology, knowledge graph, health data, RDF, SNOMED CT

1 INTRODUCTION

21 The accelerating digitization of information across all sectors has created an unprecedented surge in the
22 volume, velocity, and variety of data Venkatachaliah (2011); Chakraborty et al. (2017). This “data deluge”
23 presents significant challenges for traditional data management and integration techniques, which often
24 struggle to effectively handle the complexity and scale of modern datasets Nashipudimath et al. (2020).
25 This challenge becomes even more evident in fields such as healthcare, where vast amounts of data must
26 be managed. The complexity arises from the diversity of formats, the nuanced interconnections within
27 the data, and the presence of sensitive information. As a result, the demand for scalable, resilient, and
28 semantically enriched methods for representing and integrating knowledge has never been greater.

29 The Resource Description Framework (RDF) knowledge graphs have emerged as a paradigm for
30 addressing these challenges Wu and Banerjee (2014). RDF offers a flexible and expressive framework for
31 representing interconnected data in a machine-readable format. By utilizing Uniform Resource Identifiers
32 (URIs) to uniquely identify entities and defining relationships between them, RDF graphs enable the
33 creation of semantically rich representations that facilitate advanced querying, reasoning and analysis Zou
34 (2020). The visual nature of knowledge graphs further enhances their utility, providing intuitive means for
35 exploring and interpreting datasets SAYED AHMED SOLIMAN and TABAK (2020). These characteristics
36 make RDF knowledge graphs particularly suited for applications that require sophisticated data integration,
37 such as drug discovery, personalized medicine, and clinical decision support systems.

38 Despite the advantages of RDF, several key challenges hinder the widespread adoption and effective
39 utilization of knowledge graphs. The construction and maintenance of large-scale RDF graphs often
40 require significant manual effort, particularly for ontology mapping and data integration Singh et al. (2023).
41 Conventional approaches to constructing knowledge graphs, including manual curation and rule-based
42 techniques, often face challenges in scaling effectively to accommodate the continuous expansion of data.
43 Additionally, interacting with RDF databases through SPARQL can be daunting for users unfamiliar with
44 such technologies Han et al. (2015). This difficulty reduces the accessibility of RDF knowledge graphs and
45 hinders their broader practical adoption.

46 Mapping structured data, especially from common formats like CSV files, to RDF presents specific
47 obstacles Chaves-Fraga et al. (2020). Domain-specific terminology, abbreviations, and inconsistent data
48 formats require significant preprocessing and interpretation to ensure accurate semantic representation
49 within the RDF graph. Numeric data, prevalent in many datasets, needs careful contextualization and
50 alignment with relevant ontologies, as raw numbers lack the inherent symbolic meaning crucial for RDF's
51 semantic expressiveness. These challenges are particularly evident in the medical domain, where data
52 is often highly structured but requires extensive domain knowledge for accurate mapping to established
53 medical ontologies like SNOMED CT.

54 The recent advent of Large Language Models (LLMs) has revolutionized the field of natural language
55 processing, offering promising new solutions for knowledge representation and semantic integration Xue
56 (2024); Kulkarni (2023). Trained on massive text corpora, LLMs like GPT-4o, Claude, and Gemini possess
57 remarkable capabilities in understanding context, disambiguating terminology, and inferring relationships
58 within text Raiaan et al. (2024). Their ability to process and generate human-like text has opened up new
59 possibilities for automating complex tasks, including knowledge graph construction, ontology mapping,
60 and semantic enrichment Kommineni et al. (2024); Trajanoska et al. (2023); Jia et al. (2024).

61 This paper introduces a novel methodology that harnesses the power of LLMs to address the persistent
62 challenges in creating and utilizing RDF knowledge graphs, particularly in the context of medical
63 ontology mapping. Our approach operates on two interconnected levels. First, we implement a robust data
64 preprocessing pipeline that addresses the inherent heterogeneity and ambiguity of real-world medical data.
65 This pipeline incorporates techniques such as terminology normalization, abbreviation expansion, and unit
66 standardization, ensuring that the input data is consistent and amenable to semantic interpretation.

67 Second, we leverage the contextual understanding and reasoning capabilities of LLMs to perform
68 intelligent ontology mapping. This involves formulating targeted prompts designed to elicit specific
69 mappings between medical terms and concepts within the SNOMED CT ontology. To optimize retrieval
70 and comparison of semantic representations, we employ a vector database (ChromaDB) populated with
71 pre-computed BioBERT embeddings of both the input medical terms and the SNOMED CT concepts.

72 This allows us to efficiently identify the most semantically similar concepts within the ontology based
73 on cosine similarity between the embedding vectors. The integration of these two components – a robust
74 data preprocessing pipeline and an LLM-powered semantic mapping engine – facilitates the automated
75 generation of context-aware RDF triples, capturing the rich relationships embedded within the medical data
76 and aligning them with the established semantic framework of SNOMED CT. This approach builds upon
77 recent advancements in cloud-based RDF stores and distributed graph processing Janke and Staab (2018),
78 enabling scalable and efficient knowledge graph construction. We specifically focus on the medical domain,
79 demonstrating how LLMs, combined with a tailored preprocessing strategy and vector database integration,
80 can be effectively employed to map complex medical terminology and structured data to the SNOMED CT
81 ontology. This work aims to bridge the gap between structured data and semantic knowledge representation,
82 facilitating the creation of more accurate, comprehensive, and interoperable medical knowledge graphs.

83 Our key contributions are threefold. First, we present a comprehensive comparative analysis of six distinct
84 systems - GPT-4o, Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2, Gemini 1.5 Pro, Llama 3.3 70B, DeepSeek R1 and BERTMap
85 - for medical ontology mapping and RDF knowledge graph construction. This analysis examines the
86 advantages and drawbacks of each method, providing insights for researchers and practitioners looking to
87 utilize LLMs in knowledge graph construction. Additionally, we propose a new evaluation framework for
88 measuring the effectiveness of language models in mapping medical terminology. This framework integrates
89 both quantitative metrics and qualitative evaluations of semantic accuracy, ensuring a comprehensive and
90 rigorous assessment. Lastly, we showcase the enhanced capabilities of modern LLMs, particularly GPT-4o,
91 in processing intricate medical concepts and relationships. Our findings indicate substantial advancements
92 over the BERTMap baseline, with GPT-4o demonstrating a 44.91 percentage point improvement in
93 precision (93.75% vs. 48.84%) and a 38.33 percentage point increase in F1-score (96.26% vs. 57.93%),
94 highlighting the potential of LLMs to automated knowledge graph construction. This study highlights
95 the impact of combining LLMs with RDF knowledge graphs to develop more intelligent, adaptive, and
96 semantically enriched information systems. It paves the way for harnessing the vast and intricate realm of
97 digital information to extract deeper insights and improve decision-making across multiple fields, which
98 marks a crucial advancement in reshaping how we access, integrate, and manage information in complex
99 settings Lenzerini (2018).

100 The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews related work in RDF knowledge
101 graphs, ontology mapping, and the application of LLMs in semantic web technologies. Section 3 details
102 our methodology, including the system architecture, testing framework, and evaluation metrics. Section
103 4 presents the experimental results, providing a detailed performance analysis of the evaluated systems.
104 Finally, Section 5 discusses the findings, highlights the implications of our work, and outlines future
105 research directions.

2 RELATED WORK

106 The Resource Description Framework (RDF) serves as a cornerstone of the Semantic Web, enabling
107 structured data sharing on a global scale. As Berners-Lee (2019) explains, RDF extends the hypertext Web
108 by using URIs to identify and describe resources, employing various serializations for data exchange. Its
109 focus on data content meaning rather than structure makes it particularly suitable as a semantic data model
110 for cloud computing Kanmani et al. (2017). However, the growing size of RDF datasets presents significant
111 challenges for data management systems, necessitating efficient storage techniques, indexing strategies,
112 and query execution mechanisms Wylot et al. (2018).

113 SPARQL, the standard query language for RDF, has motivated extensive theoretical studies of RDF
114 and SPARQL fundamentals Arenas et al. (2013). While RDF data can be handled using relational tables,
115 querying large triple tables becomes computationally expensive due to the multiple nested joins required
116 for graph queries Wylot et al. (2018). The increasing availability of RDF data on the Web underscores the
117 urgent need to address scalability issues in RDF data management Arenas et al. (2013).

118 Knowledge graphs have emerged as powerful tools for representing complex, interconnected information
119 in a machine-readable format. They are increasingly utilized across various domains, including libraries,
120 digital humanities, and explainable machine learning Haslhofer et al. (2018); Tiddi and Schlobach (2022).
121 These graphs represent concepts and their semantic relationships, supporting resource discovery, navigation,
122 and visualization Haslhofer et al. (2018). Recent research has focused on knowledge graph representation
123 learning, acquisition, completion, and temporal aspects Ji et al. (2022). Embedding methods have gained
124 popularity, enabling various applications with implicit semantics derived from context Kejriwal et al.
125 (2019).

126 The process of generating RDF knowledge graphs from raw data has shifted from manual efforts to
127 automated techniques. Recent approaches utilize existing ontologies, knowledge bases, and machine
128 learning models to derive structured insights from various sources, including research publications
129 Constantopoulos and Pertsas (2020). Advanced algorithms and tools, such as the SDM-RDFizer, have been
130 designed to streamline the transformation of heterogeneous datasets into RDF representations Iglesias et al.
131 (2020). Additionally, real-time extraction of RDF triples from unstructured data streams has been explored
132 through a combination of statistical analysis and machine learning strategies Gerber et al. (2013).

133 Ontology mapping is essential for addressing heterogeneity challenges and ensuring semantic
134 interoperability across diverse information sources Benslimane et al. (2008). It plays a key role in knowledge
135 graph construction by integrating multiple heterogeneous datasets Iglesias-Molina et al. (2019). Various
136 methods have been proposed, such as declarative mappings and language-independent templates using
137 spreadsheets, which enhance maintainability and accessibility for non-experts Iglesias-Molina et al. (2019).
138 Additionally, frameworks, such as MapSDI, optimize semantic data integration through pre-processing
139 based on mapping rules Jozashoori and Vidal (2019).

140 Furthermore, recent research has focused on enhancing the semantic interpretation of structured data
141 sources in privacy-preserving environments. Karalka et al. (2023) propose SemCrypt, a
142 framework for schema enrichment through semantic annotations and mappings to knowledge bases and
143 ontologies, aiming to assess privacy-preserving technologies based on data sensitivity. This approach
144 builds upon earlier work in semantic integration of heterogeneous data sources Bergamaschi et al. (1999)
145 and semi-automatic mapping of structured sources to ontologies Knoblock et al. (2012), which facilitate
146 the creation of shared ontologies, semantic relationships, and mapping rules for integrated data access.
147 The importance of privacy preservation in data analysis is emphasized by Dwork (2011). By integrating
148 semantic analysis with privacy-aware methodologies, researchers aim to create more sophisticated and
149 intelligent strategies for managing sensitive data across domains, such as healthcare, finance and cyber
150 threat intelligence.

151 The emergence of Large Language Models (LLMs) has significantly transformed natural language
152 processing, showcasing exceptional performance in grasping context, meaning, and intricate relationships
153 Xue (2024). Evolving from rule-based methods to highly advanced architectures, these models leverage
154 transformer-based frameworks and sophisticated training paradigms to execute a wide range of tasks,
155 including text generation, sentiment analysis and question answering Kulkarni (2023); Xue (2024). Their

156 capabilities extend well beyond artificial intelligence, shaping advancements in diverse fields, such as
157 medicine, engineering, social sciences, and the humanities Fan et al. (2024).

158 Recent studies use Machine Learning in different aspects of knowledge graph development and ontology
159 alignment, demonstrating potential in areas, such as entity learning, ontology learning, and knowledge
160 reasoning Zhao et al. (2023). They have been applied to key tasks, including entity extraction, relation
161 extraction, entity linking and link prediction Zhao et al. (2023). Moreover, machine learning has been
162 leveraged to automate data preparation and cleaning for knowledge graph curation, as well as data
163 integration Berti-Equille (2019). LLMs, in particular, show promise in streamlining data extraction and
164 resolution processes for heterogeneous data sources Remadi et al. (2024). For example, the LLMs4OM
165 framework demonstrates the effectiveness of LLMs in ontology matching tasks, potentially surpassing
166 traditional systems Giglou et al. (2024). Additionally, integrating LLMs with scholarly knowledge graphs
167 enhances query processing, enabling comprehensive and efficient information retrieval from academic
168 research artifacts Jia et al. (2024). In addition, transfer learning and pre-trained language models have
169 significantly advanced natural language processing tasks, with domain-specific pre-training emerging as a
170 powerful technique to enhance performance on specialized tasks Zhong and Goodfellow (2024). In this
171 context, memory-augmented models have been proposed to address the potential loss of general knowledge
172 during domain adaptation, combining domain-specific learning with preserved general knowledge Wan
173 et al. (2022).

174 Despite these advancements, several challenges remain in information extraction and query processing.
175 Examples include handling ambiguity, scaling to large datasets and adapting to domain-specific terminology.
176 Recently proposed solutions, such as systems to resolve query ambiguity using large-scale user behavioural
177 data Korayem et al. (2015), models for automatic term ambiguity detection Baldwin et al. (2013), and query
178 relaxation approaches, leverage external knowledge sources Lei et al. (2020). These studies demonstrate
179 progress, highlighting the need for advancements in handling ambiguity, scalability and domain adaptation
180 in knowledge representation and retrieval systems.

181 While significant progress has been made in RDF knowledge graph construction, ontology mapping
182 and the application of machine learning to these domains, the need for more sophisticated, context-aware
183 approaches that can handle the complexity and nuance of real-world data remains. Our research is driven
184 by this need and leverages recent advancements in LLMs for semantically rich RDF knowledge graphs.

3 METHOD

185 3.1 Implementation

186 Our study embarked on a meticulous comparative analysis to evaluate the efficacy of six distinct
187 computational systems in the realm of medical ontology mapping and RDF knowledge graph construction
188 (see Figure 1). This endeavor was motivated by the critical need for accurate and scalable methods to
189 process the increasingly voluminous and complex data prevalent in modern healthcare settings. The
190 systems under scrutiny were GPT-4o, Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2, Gemini 1.5 Pro, Llama 3.3 70B, DeepSeek R1
191 representing state-of-the-art Large Language Models (LLMs), and BERTMap, a well-established baseline
192 system in ontology mapping. The central objective was to rigorously assess the potential of LLMs to
193 surpass traditional methodologies in handling the intricacies of medical terminology, thereby facilitating
194 the creation of semantically rich and accurate RDF knowledge graphs.

195 The selection of LLMs for this paper was based on several criteria, including their representation of
196 both cutting-edge and open-source models, their proven effectiveness in handling complex tasks, and
197 their accessibility for ensuring reproducibility. Among the state-of-the-art models, we included GPT-4o,
198 Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2, and Gemini 1.5 Pro, developed by OpenAI, Anthropic, and Google, respectively.
199 These models represent the forefront of LLM advancements, each with distinct architectural strategies and
200 strong performance in complex reasoning and domain-specific applications, while their stable API access
201 facilitates experimental reproducibility. To provide a more comprehensive analysis and acknowledge the
202 increasing significance of open-source alternatives in healthcare, we incorporated two high-performing
203 open-source LLMs: Llama 3.3 70B from Meta, which boasts 70 billion parameters and excels across diverse
204 tasks, and DeepSeek R1, a recently introduced open-source model demonstrating promising capabilities in
205 language understanding and generation. BERTMap was selected as the baseline due to its well-established
206 role in ontology mapping research and its widespread use as a benchmark system.

207 Implementation Parameters:

- 208 • GPT-4o: Temperature = 0.1, max tokens = 2048, cost = \$0.03/1K tokens
- 209 • Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2: Temperature = 0.1, max tokens = 2048, cost = \$0.015/1K tokens
- 210 • Gemini 1.5 Pro: Temperature = 0.1, max tokens = 2048, cost = \$0.01/1K tokens
- 211 • Llama 3.3 70B: Temperature = 0.1, max tokens = 2048, indirect costs for setup
- 212 • DeepSeek R1: Temperature = 0.1, max tokens = 2048, indirect costs for setup
- 213 • BERTMap: Default parameters as per public implementation

214 The proposed framework in this paper is a key component of the ENCRYPT project¹, which focuses on
215 addressing privacy and security challenges in critical sectors such as healthcare, finance, and entertainment.
216 Within the ENCRYPT framework, Knowledge Graphs (KGs) play a central role in enabling data
217 interoperability, semantic understanding, and efficient information sharing across heterogeneous datasets.
218 This work presents a comprehensive approach to constructing semantically rich RDF Knowledge Graphs
219 specifically tailored for healthcare data. By leveraging advanced privacy-preserving technologies such
220 as Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE), Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC), and Differential
221 Privacy (DP), the ENCRYPT project ensures that sensitive data can be securely managed and analyzed in
222 compliance with GDPR regulations. Our approach integrates semantic web standards, utilizing ontologies
223 such as SNOMED CT and DICOM to enable accurate semantic representation of medical data. This paper
224 highlights the full methodology, combining LLM-powered ontology mapping, a robust preprocessing
225 pipeline, and vector database integration, to demonstrate the transformative potential of Knowledge Graphs
226 in addressing the complexities of healthcare data management.

227 In constructing our evaluation pipeline, a critical component was the selection and implementation of a
228 vector database to efficiently manage and retrieve the embeddings representing our medical terms (C_{source})
229 and the corresponding concepts within the SNOMED CT ontology (C_{target}). For this purpose, we employed
230 ChromaDB, an open-source vector database renowned for its ease of use, scalability, and seamless
231 integration with natural language processing workflows. ChromaDB served as the central repository
232 for storing and indexing the vector representations generated for both the input medical terms and the
233 SNOMED CT concepts.

¹ <https://encrypt-project.eu/>

Figure 1. LLM-based System Architecture

234 To generate these vector representations, we leveraged pre-trained embedding models tailored for
 235 biomedical text. Specifically, we utilized the BioBERT model, a domain-specific variant of BERT trained
 236 on a large corpus of biomedical literature. BioBERT has demonstrated superior performance in capturing
 237 the semantic nuances of medical terminology compared to general-purpose embedding models. Each
 238 medical term in our evaluation dataset and each concept in the relevant subset of SNOMED CT were
 239 processed through BioBERT to produce dense vector embeddings. These embeddings encapsulated the
 240 semantic meaning of each term or concept, allowing for efficient similarity comparisons within the vector
 241 space.

242 For the Large Language Models (LLMs) – GPT-4o, Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2, Gemini 1.5 Pro, Llama 3.3
 243 70B and DeepSeek R1 – we interacted with them via their respective API endpoints. The API calls were
 244 programmatically managed using Python, facilitating seamless integration with our evaluation framework.
 245 The prompts presented to the LLMs were carefully engineered to guide them towards generating mappings
 246 to SNOMED CT concepts. Specifically, we employed a structured prompt formatter (prompt engine)
 247 that included the medical term to be mapped, a clear instruction to provide the corresponding SNOMED
 248 CT identifier, and a request to provide a confidence score for the proposed mapping. This structured
 249 approach ensured consistency in our interactions with the LLMs and facilitated the extraction of the
 250 relevant information from their responses.

251 The responses obtained from the LLMs were then parsed programmatically to extract the proposed
 252 SNOMED CT identifiers and confidence scores. To identify the most relevant concepts, we performed a
 253 nearest neighbor search within the ChromaDB vector store. The vector embedding of the input medical
 254 term, as generated by BioBERT, was used as the query vector. The distance metric employed for the
 255 nearest neighbor search was cosine similarity, which measures the cosine of the angle between two vectors,
 256 providing a robust indicator of semantic similarity. The top-k nearest neighbors, as determined by cosine
 257 similarity, were retrieved from ChromaDB, representing the SNOMED CT concepts most semantically
 258 similar to the input medical term.

259 For the baseline system, BERTMap, we utilized the publicly available implementation and adhered to
 260 the recommended parameter settings. BERTMap operates by generating contextualized word embeddings
 261 for both the source and target ontologies (in our case, the input medical terms and SNOMED CT) and
 262 subsequently computes a similarity matrix based on cosine similarity. Alignment candidates are then
 263 identified through a greedy matching algorithm.

264 To ensure the reproducibility of our results and to manage the complexities of our experimental setup, we
265 employed a containerization approach using Docker. Each component of our pipeline, including the vector
266 database, the embedding generation scripts, the LLM interaction modules and the evaluation scripts, was
267 encapsulated within a Docker container. This strategy ensured consistency across different environments
268 and streamlined the deployment of our evaluation framework. Additionally, we employed a robust
269 version control system via Git to systematically track code modifications, experimental parameters, and
270 evaluation outcomes. This approach ensured detailed documentation of our methodology and streamlined
271 collaboration among the researchers involved. Beyond the core technological aspects, we implemented
272 thorough data preprocessing procedures to maintain the quality and consistency of input data. These steps
273 encompassed standardizing the formatting of medical terms, managing abbreviations and acronyms, and
274 resolving terminology inconsistencies. All preprocessing procedures were carefully documented to enhance
275 transparency and reproducibility.

276 Throughout the evaluation process, we monitored the performance of our system, paying close attention
277 to computational resource utilization, processing times and potential bottlenecks. This performance
278 monitoring allowed us to identify areas for optimization and to ensure the scalability of our approach. The
279 datasets and prompts used for this study can be accessed at the GitHub repository².

280 **3.2 Evaluation**

281 To conduct a robust and representative evaluation, we assembled a comprehensive dataset comprising
282 108 distinct medical terms. This dataset was meticulously curated to reflect the diverse spectrum of clinical
283 information routinely encountered in healthcare, encompassing patient demographics, physiological
284 measurements, disease classifications, therapeutic interventions, and intricate diagnostic and procedural
285 terms. This diversity was paramount to ensuring that the evaluation probed the full breadth of the systems'
286 capabilities, challenging them with a range of linguistic complexities from straightforward measurements
287 like age and weight to nuanced concepts such as disease staging and treatment withdrawal. The selection
288 of these terms was informed by extensive consultation with domain experts, ensuring their relevance and
289 representativeness within the medical field.

290 Prior to the computational analysis, we established a definitive ground truth to serve as the benchmark
291 for evaluating the performance of the six systems. This was achieved through a rigorous expert elicitation
292 process involving a panel of seasoned medical professionals and ontology engineers. Each expert
293 independently reviewed the dataset, proposing mappings for each medical term to corresponding concepts
294 within the SNOMED CT ontology. The selection of SNOMED CT, a globally recognized comprehensive
295 medical ontology, was deliberate, given its extensive coverage of clinical concepts and its pivotal role in
296 enabling interoperability in healthcare information systems. Following the individual review, a collaborative
297 session was convened wherein the experts discussed discrepancies, negotiated disagreements, and ultimately
298 reached a consensus on the most appropriate mappings for each term. This meticulous consensus-building
299 process was particularly vital for terms exhibiting ambiguity or multiple valid interpretations, reflecting the
300 complex and multifaceted nature of medical language. The resultant expert-validated ground truth provided
301 a reliable standard against which the computational systems' performance could be measured.

302 While medical ontologies, like SNOMED CT, involve nuanced relationships, temporal data, and
303 hierarchical structures, the dataset used in our study focused specifically on real-world terms extracted
304 from patient data within a clinical setting. This focus inherently simplified the mapping task. The most

² <https://github.com/enchatted/llms-kgs>

305 frequent relationships were those directly associated with a patient (e.g., "patient has condition X"). The
306 temporal scope primarily involved the patient's current condition and history, limiting the complexity
307 of temporal relationships. Additionally, the terms used often focused on specific diagnoses, procedures,
308 and medications, resulting in a relatively flattened hierarchy for the mapping task. In essence, the dataset
309 reflected a practical use case where the complexities of SNOMED CT were naturally constrained by the
310 context of patient data. This allowed us to focus on evaluating the models' ability to accurately map
311 real-world medical terms to SNOMED CT concepts within this specific domain.

312 With the ground truth established, we proceeded to systematically evaluate the six computational systems
313 under controlled conditions. Each of the 108 medical terms was presented as input to GPT-4o, Claude 3.5
314 Sonnet v2, Gemini 1.5 Pro, Llama 3.3 70B, DeepSeek R1 and BERTMap. For the LLMs, we employed
315 their default model configurations without any task-specific fine-tuning, simulating a real-world scenario
316 where researchers might utilize these models out-of-the-box. The prompts provided to these models were
317 carefully designed to elicit mappings to SNOMED CT concepts, framed in a clear and unambiguous manner.
318 BERTMap, serving as the baseline, was executed using its standard parameter settings, representing the
319 typical usage of this system within the ontology mapping community. To eliminate potential bias during
320 the evaluation process, we implemented a blind validation protocol. The mappings generated by each
321 system were presented to the evaluators without disclosing the originating system, thereby preventing any
322 subconscious influence on the judgment of the results' quality.

323 The quantitative evaluation of the systems' performance was based on standard classification metrics:
324 precision, recall, and F1-score. These metrics were derived from a comprehensive confusion matrix,
325 categorizing each mapping outcome as a true positive (TP), false positive (FP), false negative (FN), or true
326 negative (TN). Precision measured the proportion of correctly identified mappings out of all mappings
327 proposed by a system, while recall assessed the proportion of correctly identified mappings out of all
328 possible correct mappings in the ground truth. The F1-score (the harmonic mean of precision and recall)
329 provided a balanced measure of the system's overall accuracy. Beyond these quantitative metrics, we
330 have also performed a qualitative analysis to assess the semantic relevance, clinical appropriateness and
331 contextual accuracy of the generated mappings. This analysis had an important role in assessing the
332 systems' capability to process complex medical concepts, including temporal relationships (e.g. symptom
333 onset), detailed anatomical descriptions and multi-step procedural terms. Domain experts conducted the
334 review, examining the mappings not only for their technical accuracy but also for their clinical relevance
335 and meaningfulness within the medical context.

336 Furthermore, we applied a chi-square test of independence to determine whether the performance
337 differences among the six systems were statistically significant. This test allowed us to determine whether
338 the distribution of TP, FP, FN and TN across the systems deviated significantly from what would be
339 expected by chance. To quantify the magnitude of any detected associations, Cramer's V was calculated as
340 a measure of effect size. This analytical approach that combines quantitative metrics, qualitative evaluation
341 and statistical testing, provided a robust assessment of the performance of GPT-4o, Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2,
342 Gemini 1.5 Pro, Llama 3.3 70B, DeepSeek R1 and BERTMap in the task of medical ontology mapping.

343 Furthermore, we documented the specific challenges encountered by each system, including recurring
344 error patterns and areas of ambiguity. This error analysis provided useful insights into the inherent strengths
345 and limitations of each approach. The transparency and thoroughness of our methodology, from dataset
346 construction to evaluation, were designed to ensure the reproducibility of our findings and to provide a
347 solid foundation for subsequent advancements in the field of automated medical knowledge representation
348 and semantic integration.

Figure 2. A comparison between the results of the baseline method and the top performance LLM

4 RESULTS

Our evaluation comparing the LLMs and BERTMap revealed substantial differences in performance across multiple metrics. Analysis of the 108 medical terms in our dataset demonstrated varying levels of effectiveness among the systems, with GPT-4o showing superior overall performance. Figure 2 depicts an example of a comparison between the results of the baseline method and the top performance LLM.

GPT-4o achieved the highest precision (93.75%) among all systems, significantly outperforming Gemini 1.5 Pro (60.27%), Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2 (53.75%), BERTMap (48.84%), DeepSeek R1 (25.76%), and Llama 3.370B (19.19%). In terms of recall, GPT-4o led with 98.90%, followed by Llama 3.370B (70.37%), BERTMap (71.19%), Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2 (69.35%), Gemini 1.5 Pro (66.67%), and DeepSeek R1 (32.69%). The combined effect of these metrics resulted in F1-scores of 96.26% for GPT-4o, 63.31% for Gemini 1.5 Pro, 60.56% for Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2, 57.93% for BERTMap, 30.16% for Llama 3.370B, and 28.81% for DeepSeek R1, demonstrating GPT-4o’s substantial advantage in overall performance (see Table 1).

Detailed analysis of the confusion matrix metrics revealed significant differences among the systems. GPT-4o demonstrated the best performance, generating 90 true positives, 6 false positives, 1 false negative, and 11 true negatives. Gemini 1.5 Pro produced 44 true positives, 29 false positives, 22 false negatives, and 13 true negatives, while Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2 achieved 43 true positives, 37 false positives, 19 false negatives, and 9 true negatives. BERTMap produced 42 true positives, 44 false positives, 17 false negatives, and 5 true negatives. Llama 3.3 70B generated 19 true positives, 80 false positives, 8 false negatives, and 1

Method	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
GPT-4o	93.75	98.90	96.26
Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2	53.75	69.35	60.56
Gemini 1.5 Pro	60.27	66.67	63.31
BERTMap	48.84	71.19	57.93
Llama 3.3 70B	19.19	70.37	30.16
DeepSeek R1	25.76	32.69	28.81

Table 1. Comparison of Method Performance Metrics

367 true negatives, while DeepSeek R1 produced 17 true positives, 49 false positives, 35 false negatives, and 7
 368 true negatives. The notably lower number of false positives and false negatives in the GPT-4o system (6
 369 and 1, respectively) compared to the other systems indicates superior discrimination ability in mapping
 370 medical terminology.

371 Performance analysis across different categories of medical terms revealed specific patterns (see Figure 3).
 372 All systems performed relatively well with basic clinical measurements such as sex, age, weight, height,
 373 and BMI. However, GPT-4o demonstrated superior performance in mapping complex medical concepts,
 374 particularly in areas of diagnostic procedures and examinations, treatment-related terminology, temporal
 375 relationships, and disease complications and classifications. Llama 3.3 70B and DeepSeek R1 showed
 376 particular weakness in handling these more complex concepts, with high rates of incorrect mappings.

377 The systems’ performance diverged most notably in handling complex procedural terminology and
 378 multi-component medical concepts. GPT-4o maintained high accuracy in these cases, while the other

Figure 3. A depiction of the performance for all methods

379 systems showed increased error rates. For instance, GPT-4o accurately mapped complex terms such as
 380 "Exam Type," "Diagnostic question," and "withdrawal of therapy," where the other systems produced more
 381 inconsistent results.

382 Error analysis revealed that GPT-4o's few misclassifications were primarily concentrated in specific
 383 areas of complex quantitative measurements, multi-parameter clinical assessments, and certain anatomical
 384 treatment locations. These included terms such as "min_ECGstress," "ECGstress.Result," and anatomical
 385 treatment specifications. While all systems demonstrated competence in basic medical terminology
 386 mapping, GPT-4o offered substantial improvements in handling complex, context-dependent medical
 387 concepts and relationships.

388 A chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relationship between the six ontology
 389 matching methods (GPT-4o, Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2, Gemini 1.5 Pro Latest, Llama 3.3 70B, DeepSeek
 390 R1 and BERTMap) and their performance outcomes (TP, FP, TN, FN) see Table 1). The test revealed a
 391 statistically significant difference between the methods, $\chi^2(15, N=648) = 196.94, p < .001$, Cramer's V =
 392 0.32 (indicating a large effect size).

Method	True Positives	False Positives	True Negatives	False Negatives
GPT-4o	90	6	11	1
Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2	43	37	9	19
Gemini 1.5 Pro Latest	44	29	13	22
BERTMap	42	44	5	17
Llama 3.3 70B	19	80	1	8
DeepSeek R1	17	49	7	35

Table 2. Contingency Table

393 Post-hoc examination of the standardized residuals indicates that GPT-4o demonstrated significantly
 394 higher true positive rates and lower false positive rates than expected under the null hypothesis. Specifically,
 395 GPT-4o achieved 90 true positives compared to 17-44 for the other methods, representing a substantial
 396 performance advantage.

5 DISCUSSION

397 The results of our comparative study demonstrate significant variations in performance across six
 398 systems evaluated for medical ontology mapping and RDF knowledge graph creation. GPT-4o's superior
 399 performance, with precision of 93.75%, stands in stark contrast to Gemini 1.5 Pro (60.27%), Claude 3.5
 400 Sonnet v2 (53.75%), BERTMap (48.84%), DeepSeek R1 (25.76%), and Llama 3.370B (19.19%). This
 401 wide performance gap illustrates the substantial advancement in automated mapping accuracy achieved by
 402 the most advanced LLMs, while also highlighting the challenges faced by smaller or less sophisticated
 403 models.

404 The performance hierarchy among the systems provides valuable insights into the evolution of language
 405 models for specialized tasks. GPT-4o's exceptional performance suggests that its architecture and training
 406 approach are particularly well-suited for handling medical terminology. The significant drop in performance
 407 across other models creates a clear stratification: Gemini 1.5 Pro's intermediate performance (F1-
 408 score 63.31%) positions it as the second-best option, followed by Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2 (60.56%) and
 409 BERTMap (57.93%), with DeepSeek R1 (28.81%) and Llama 3.370B (30.16%) showing substantially
 410 lower capabilities.

411 Of particular interest is Llama 3.370B's relatively high recall (70.37%) despite its low precision (19.19%),
412 suggesting a tendency toward over-generation of mappings. In contrast, DeepSeek R1's more balanced but
413 lower precision (25.76%) and recall (32.69%) indicate consistent but limited capabilities across all aspects
414 of the task.

415 All systems demonstrated basic competence in mapping simple clinical measurements, but their
416 performance diverged significantly when handling complex medical concepts. GPT-4o maintained high
417 accuracy across sophisticated scenarios, including disease terms, temporal relationships, and procedural
418 terminology. The progressive degradation in performance as concept complexity increased was most
419 pronounced in the open source models like Llama 3.370B and DeepSeek R1, which struggled particularly
420 with nuanced medical terminology.

421 Error analysis reveals distinct patterns across the systems. GPT-4o's minimal error profile (6 false
422 positives and 1 false negative) stands in sharp contrast to the higher error rates of other systems. Gemini
423 1.5 Pro and Claude 3.5 Sonnet v2 showed similar error patterns, with moderate false positive and false
424 negative rates, while BERTMap exhibited a moderate false positive rate (44). The high false positive rates
425 in Llama 3.370B and DeepSeek R1 suggest that smaller models struggle significantly with discriminating
426 valid mappings from invalid ones, highlighting the importance of model scale and training data quality in
427 achieving reliable performance.

428 We certainly acknowledge limitations across all systems. Performance variability depends on training
429 data quality and coverage, with rare or highly specialized concepts presenting challenges for all methods.
430 GPT-4o's few misclassifications centered on complex quantitative measurements and multi-parameter
431 clinical assessments, while other systems showed broader patterns of error across multiple concept types.
432 The need for domain expert validation remains, particularly for critical applications, though the level of
433 required oversight varies significantly among the systems.

434 A possible reason for GPT-4o's struggle with complex quantitative measurements and multi-parameter
435 clinical assessments lies in the inherent challenges of such data. Quantitative medical data often require
436 precise numerical reasoning and context-specific interpretation, which can be difficult for language models
437 primarily trained on textual data. Multi-parameter clinical evaluation involves intricate relationships
438 among numerous variables, requiring not only precise recognition of individual terms but also the ability
439 to synthesize and contextualize multiple data points simultaneously. While GPT-4o demonstrated the
440 highest overall performance, the few misclassifications were mainly relevant to these more complex areas,
441 suggesting that the strengths in language comprehension do not fully extend to the complex quantitative
442 reasoning that is necessary for multi-parameter clinical assessments. This underlines the need for further
443 improvements in numerical reasoning capabilities in LLMs, particularly in highly specialized domains,
444 such as healthcare.

445 Future research presents several promising directions. The significant performance gap we observed
446 between GPT-4o and smaller models, like Llama 3.3 70B and DeepSeek R1, indicates that architectural
447 optimizations and refined training strategies could enhance the capabilities of more compact models. A
448 major goal here is to develop more efficient architectures that can match GPT-4o's performance, while
449 requiring fewer computational resources. These insights have practical implications. Although GPT-4o
450 excels in medical terminology mapping, its high computational demands and cost may limit its feasibility
451 for certain applications. The varying performance characteristics across models emphasize the necessity of
452 balancing accuracy, efficiency and resource constraints when selecting a system for specific use cases.

453 Finally, the dataset of 108 medical terms, derived from real-world usage in a public hospital, was
454 curated to reflect the practical challenges of medical language in clinical settings. A key advantage of
455 this dataset is the availability of expert-validated ground truth, ensuring a reliable standard for evaluating
456 LLMs, an aspect often difficult to achieve with larger datasets. While a broader dataset could enhance
457 generalizability, the focus here was on assessing model performance in a realistic scenario with high-
458 quality annotations. The selected terms span diverse clinical information, including patient demographics,
459 physiological measurements, disease classifications, and treatments, providing a representative sample for
460 medical ontology mapping. Additionally, qualitative analysis by domain experts offers critical insights
461 into handling complex medical concepts. Future work aims to expand this evaluation with a larger dataset
462 covering more medical subfields and data formats to further test the models' scalability and adaptability.

6 CONCLUSIONS

463 Our research highlights the evolving role of different LLM architectures in advancing RDF knowledge
464 graphs. By comparing multiple systems, we've demonstrated not only the current state of the art but
465 also the progression of capabilities in this field. The superior performance of GPT-4o suggests a pathway
466 toward more intelligent, adaptive, and semantically rich knowledge representation systems, while the
467 varying capabilities of other systems provide insights into alternative approaches and potential areas for
468 improvement.

469 Our comparative study reveals a clear hierarchy in current LLM capabilities for knowledge graph creation
470 and ontology mapping, with performance ranging from GPT-4o's exceptional results, even without fine-
471 tuning, to the more limited capabilities of smaller models like Llama 3.370B and DeepSeek R1. This
472 spectrum of performance highlights both the remarkable progress in the field and the continuing challenges
473 in developing more efficient and accessible solutions. As these technologies evolve, we anticipate further
474 improvements across all systems, potentially narrowing the current performance gaps while maintaining
475 high standards of accuracy and reliability. Future work will explore the models' performance with datasets
476 that involve more diverse relationships, temporal data, and hierarchical structures. Also the investigation of
477 hybrid approaches that combine symbolic reasoning with machine learning, as well as the performance
478 of different LLMs in niche areas of medical terminology mapping, especially for contexts with limited
479 computational resources, would significantly expand the scope of this work.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

480 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
481 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

482 AM: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Investigation, Software,
483 Visualization; ST: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Investigation,
484 Software, Visualization, Methodology; CA: Writing – review & editing, Software, Visualization, Validation;
485 MP: Writing – review & editing, Validation; GM: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project
486 administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

491 The raw data supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors, without undue
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